

Supplementary Material 5. Complete Qualitative Dataset: Themes, Codes, and Representative Quotes

Table S4.

Results of the Inductive Content Analysis.

Raw data themes (k = 32)	First-order themes (k = 4)	General dimensions (k = 2)
<p>“it's the same as you're in anxiety or something you're just like holding your hand very tight”</p> <p>“Yeah, I kind of felt anxious”</p> <p>“Yeah, like dominated me kind of”</p> <p>“I was just like my perception was just like stop as fast as you can like take your hand out”</p> <p>“It didn't feel cold. It started to feel sharp. So it's like it's not the coldness that got to me”</p> <p>“It's like a sharp stabby type of pain. That's what changed”</p> <p>“were very stressful. It was almost painful and I wanted to like almost like remove my hand from the water immediately”</p> <p>“Like a, I don't know what to say, it's kind of like a rise a little bit in heart rate”</p> <p>“At first it became, it wasn't really anything too intense but towards the end it got a little bit more painful.”</p> <p>“So originally it was really painful and then I would say about halfway through it just”</p> <p>“I felt fine. But I was, I guess, a little frustrated in the sense that I felt saliva building up and I couldn't.”</p> <p>“How did I feel? I felt a little nervous.”</p> <p>“Then in the beginning it was hard to manage, but as the time continued, it was kind of actually easier to manage.”</p> <p>“I'd say I was a little nervous because I heard somebody else do it before and they're like,”</p> <p>“But yeah, I'm probably a little bit nervous but excited too.”</p> <p>“A little nervous because I don't know how cold the water was going to be, but a little nervous.”</p> <p>“A little nervous. I didn't know what to feel right before.”</p>	<p>Threat appraisal & affective strain</p>	<p>Aversive load</p>
<p>“and so it's like first trying to push through that”</p> <p>“Your hand is going to be okay to try to keep it a little longer.”</p> <p>“At some point when I was talking to myself to try to keep it, the discomfort level maybe dropped like one.”</p> <p>“but stay there and accomplish a mission”</p>	<p>Goal-directed persistence</p>	<p>Tolerance mechanisms</p>

“Determined to just keep my hand in the water”
“I guess just challenging myself really wanted to just finish through yeah just to challenge myself really”
“But then as the time went on, I felt more like, I guess determined to get to the end”
“But then I had to just keep trying and keep keep my hand in the ice cold water.”
“I was determined to make sure I kept my hand in the water as long as possible.”
“I definitely felt determinate it because I wanted to remove my hand beforehand.”
“I was trying to keep it in as much as I could but it was really painful.”
“At first anxious and then after the second time determined.”
“Because you said I had to keep it longer.”
“I was just determined to keep it in the water.”
“I was anxious at first and then determinate it towards the end.”
“I was very determinate to try and last longer than I had expected because coming in and”
“I felt determinate to try to like at”
“keep going and that was like what influenced me. Okay so you were more”
“It just kept telling myself, hold on, you got it, that's it, keep going”
“Determinate it is one for sure.”
“I just felt motivated to finish.”
“I felt determined to keep my hand in there as long as possible and that was probably”
“I would probably say my ego.”
“I was, I guess, determinate it to get it done.”
“The fact that you said to try to keep it in there as long as possible, I try to exceed my limits”
“It was definitely mentally hard. I needed to keep going. I was just waiting on...”
“and my fingers tingle a lot more. But I would tell myself to keep going. Keep going up until”
“A little anxious is right before preparing myself and then towards the like once my hand was in the water it was just like determinate it.”
“So like, so I guess like a little determination and a little like frustration because I was like, wow, like I really don't want to have my hand in here right now.”
“So a mix of determination and like mad.”
“So then you felt more like determined to keep your hand there.”
“I was determined to keep my hand in there for a very long time or until you told me to take it out”
“The fact that I just wanted to finish, I guess I just wanted to keep my hand there. I didn't want to take it out.”

"Like I wanted to be like the longest one in there"

"I was determined to push through it and then went through the..."

"I usually do cold plunges, so it was a little bit similar. So I felt fine, basically new like the feeling"

"I believe in past experiences with the cold plunges"

"But as time passed by, it kind of feels numb"

"So you just get used to it and it's kind of..."

"became a lot easier to tolerate"

"It got a little harder, but it was better to manage because it was getting numb"

"it faded away into the background and then it became very tolerable"

"No. I just think it got better as time went on that my hand felt, I guess it got used to the cold. But that's it"

"and then kind of started to feel fine after some time."

"Like it eventually started to feel like numb."

"Then as time passed, my hand began to get numb, so it started to feel a little bit okay,"

"It was more manageable as time kept going."

"Because it was it was really cold. It was really numb."

"And also trying to distract my thoughts before the exercise and trying to continue it during the exercise a little bit"

"So I can keep it in there and try to encourage myself to keep it longer"

"Probably my tolerance, probably like the pain going down and also like if I just like kind of try to distract myself"

"Just like stare at myself and not focus too much on what I was feeling in my hand"

"And I was able to control it with my breathing, so I felt pretty good"

"At first it was increasing by a lot, but then after a while, after I kept breathing and trying to focus, it decreased a little bit"

"I was kind of just praying in my head"

"And the more I focused on my breathing and not so much how cold the water was, it was more bearable"

"The breathing I was breathing heavily."

"I think I was pretty calm because the first five minutes you just have like the time to relax"

"I felt anxious because my breathing went up, my heart rate went up, so I definitely felt a little bit of distress."

"trying to focus, it decreased a little bit."

"I think my mental I was like I just looked at myself and went okay I could"

Habituation /
adaptation

Self-regulation
strategies

“But as I left my hand in longer, it wasn't as bad I would say and I was able to relax more.”
“I felt like I had to actually focus and concentrate to keep my hand in rather than before that”
“As time progressed and I focused on looking at myself in the image,”
“Probably not focusing on the pain.”
